

Health risk assessment of Aldrin and Dieldrin pesticide residues in Channa sp. from Kattemalalavadi, Hunsur Taluk.

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Abstract - Current study emphasized on assessing the pesticide residue level in common edible fish Channa sp. followed by its health risk assessment. Kattemalalavadi of Hunsur Taluk is a remote area with intensive farming activity. Tributary of Cauvery, Lakshmana Teertha flows through Kattemalalavadi hobali encouraging fishing activities. Fishes like Tilapia, Common Carp, Rohu and Channa are commonly captured and sold in local markets. Agricultural rundown is adding pesticides and heavy metals to these water bodies. Hence in the current study fish Channa was selected to assess levels of two pesticides Aldrin and Dieldrin in muscle tissue. The data thus obtained was used for health risk assessment in random population. Pesticide analysis was done by GC-MS/MS, using FSSAI Manual test method. Details about fish consumption was collected using Questionnaire with a sample size of 200 to assess the health risk, EDI, Hazard quotient (HI) and Cancer risk. Hazard quotient and cancer risk value for both Aldrin and dieldrin in Channa sp, is found to be within low risk level at thirty four gram per day consumption rate in the study area.

Keywords - Aldrin, Dieldrin, Estimated Daily Intake, Cancer Risk.

I. INTRODUCTION

Pesticide pollution encompasses the addition of chemical compounds like organochlorines, organophosphates, carbamates, and pyrethroids—into soil and water systems, leading to bioaccumulation, toxicity, and ecological imbalance (Kadiru et al., 2022) (Pathak et al., 2022) (Tahir et al., 2024). Major part of India still depends on traditional farming techniques and pesticides. Many studies have detected beyond permissible limits of pesticides in various Indian regions, posing risks to biodiversity and public health (Saha et al., 2021) (Ganaie et al., 2023) For instance, pesticide residues such as HCHs, DDTs, and chlorpyrifos have been frequently reported in water and soil matrices, often exceeding WHO and BIS standards (Rajan et al., 2023) (Mishra et al., 2024). Despite numerous studies documenting pesticide presence, there remains a fragmented understanding of their spatial distribution, sources, degradation pathways, and

cumulative impacts (Sackaria & Elango, 2020; Shah & Parveen, 2023). The current study focuses on evaluating two organochloride pesticides, aldrin and dieldrin levels in muscle tissue of fish Channa from the water body of Kattemalavadi of Hunsur taluk Mysore district. Agriculture is the chief livelihood of Hunsur, a major producer of tomato, and tobacco. Chemical fertilizers and pesticides, fungicides are generously used by farmers in these fields to name a few, Benevia, Monostar, Damal 505, Robot, Star 20, Coragen, etc. the rundown water from agricultural fields enters major water bodies like Lakshmana teertha, a tributary of Cauvery. Aldrin is quickly transformed to dieldrin either in the environmental condition or when it enters the human body. Aldrin toxicity is accompanied by an increase in the liver, headache, nausea, dizziness, and overall malaise, as well as vomiting, which is then followed by muscle twitching and convulsions. ("Health Risk Assessment and Toxicity Management of Organochlorine Pesticide," 2025).

Dieldrin might be carcinogenic through multiple modes of action. These modes of action may operate within the same tissue, or may be specific to individual tissues. (Stern, 2014). Fresh water fishes are major source of protein after red and white meat for the locals. Fishes like common carp, tilapia, catla and Channa are captured from local water bodies and are marketed. Channa a fish with traditional dietary significance is used for therapeutic purposes like wound healing, pain relieve etc. Patients recovering from surgical operations are routinely and customarily advised to eat meals containing Channa striatus in countries like Malaysia (Mohd & Abdul Manan, 2012). Fish is also rich source of protein and lipid. Despite being agriculturally active there is a huge knowledge gap about pesticide residue status in and around Hunsur taluk in specific and Mysore district in general. Channa being a bottom feeder and the fact that Dieldrin a persistent chemical generally settling in the sediment, makes a Channa an ideal sample for OCP evaluation and assessment of HQ and LCR. The current study is done a. To evaluate Aldrin and Dieldrin levels in the fish tissue. b. To assess hazard quotient and lifetime cancer risk.

II. MATERIALS AND METHOD

Sampling site

Kattemalavadi is a village near Hunsur, agriculture is the chief livelihood of the taluk. Common crops cultivated in the area are commercial crops like cotton, chilly, tobacco etc. Chemical fertilizers and pesticides, fungicides are generously used by farmers in these fields to name a few, Benevia, Monostar, Damal 505, Robot, Star 20, Coragen etc Pesticides and DAP, 20-20, Potash, Cattle manure fertilizers are commonly used. The area is also known for capturing fishes in local fishing ponds and from Lakshmana Teertha River, a tributary of Cauvery.

Source:

<https://www.google.com/maps/place/Kattemalalavadinala>,

Sample collection

Fish, Channa (Ophiocephalus sp.) samples were collected by random Sampling technique from the sample sites with the help of local fishermen. Collected the fish was transferred to the polyethylene covers, then placed them in the icebox, they were transported to the laboratory and kept in at -200C freezer before further analysis.

Sample processing, extraction and analysis of pesticides.

The sample was homogenized to obtain a uniform matrix. A 10g homogenized sample was taken in a 50 mL polypropylene centrifuge tube. 10 mL ethyl acetate was added and vortex for 1 min, 10gm anhydrous sodium sulphate was added and homogenized it at 15000 rpm for 2 minutes. Centrifuged at 5000 rpm for 5 minutes. 1 mL supernatant was taken in the Eppendorf tube containing 25 mg PSA and shaken vigorously for 30 s. Centrifuged at 10000 rpm for 5 min. the supernatant extract was taken in a GC autosampler vial. Injected the cleaned extract into the GC-MS/MS. Output was tabulated. (FSSAI Manual Test method).

Survey of fish consumption rate

Survey of Average fish consumption by locals was done by questionnaire method with a sample size of 200. Details of amount of fish consumed in grams per serving, under four categories ie., thrice in a week, once in a week, once in fortnight and once in a month was collected along with respondents age and weight.

Estimation of daily intake:

Estimated Daily intake is calculated using equation $EDI = (H \times C) / B.W.$

where H is the concentration of Aldrin/ Dieldrin [mg/kg], C is the amount of the consumed food (kg/day), B.W is the body weight (the average body weight in each cluster) (kg).

Concentration of chemical in mg/kg or mg/L

IR : Intake rate kg/day

EF : Exposure frequency (days/ year)

ED : Exposure duration

BW : Body weight in kg

AT : Averaging time for carcinogens. (Life time in days)

Hazard quotient

Hazard quotient was then calculated as ratio of estimated dietary intake and the ADI- (Acceptable daily intake) (Ar et al., 2006)

$HQ = EDI / ADI.$ (FAO, 2011)

Life time cancer risk Assessment: (US EPA, 2015) (US EPA 1989)

Cancer risk Assessment was done based on U.S. EPA, 1989 guidelines after calculating Life time average Daily dosage (LADD) for both the chemicals using following equations.

Lifetime Average Daily dosage

$$LADD = \frac{C \times IR \times EF \times ED}{BW \times AT}$$

Cancer Risk Assessment

Cancer Risk = LADD x CSF

LADD : Lifetime average daily dose

CSF : Cancer Slope Factor- U.S. EPA, 1989, (Hooker et al., 2014)

Result

Pesticide

Levels of Organochloride pesticides Aldrin and Dieldrin in the muscle tissue of Channa sp. is given in the Table 3.1. Both these pesticides are banned in India Since 2001 still their detection in the muscle tissue of fish rises concern.

Table: 3.1 Levels of Pesticide aldrin and dieldrin in the muscle tissue of Channa.sp.

Fish Species	Test Method	Unit	Aldrin	Dieldrin
Channa	FSSAI Manual	µg/kg	2.34	30.24

Dietary exposure and Risk Assessment:

EDI and Hazard quotient for two pesticides aldrin and dieldrin among people of various frequency of consumption is summarized in table 3.2. a and Table 3.2. b. For HQ, the hazard quotient the ratio between 1 and 10 refers to moderate risk, while a value above 10 could be linked to increased risk

and value of below 1 is considered low risk (Năstăsescu et al., 2020). Average of Hazard

quotient for Aldrin is 0.01224 and for dieldrin is 0.158178462 falling under low risk. Hazard quotient of 0.2 in people eating 65gm of fish per day (3 time a week) is a noteworthy finding.

Table: 3.2.a: Summary of Estimated daily intake and hazard quotient in various subpopulations based on fish consumption rate for Adrin

Fish Consumption rate	Average Consumption per day in grams	H=0.00234 (mg/kg)	Average Consumption per day in Kg ©	H×C	Average body weight B.W.	EDI=H*C/B.W	ADI	HQ=EDI/ADI
Once in 3 days	65	0.00234	0.065	0.0001521	69	0.0000022	0.0001	0.02204348
Once in a month	8.2	0.00234	0.008	0.00001872	63.3	0.0000003	0.0001	0.00295735
Once in a week	42.85	0.00234	0.0429	0.000100386	64.5	0.0000016	0.0001	0.01556372
Once in 15 days	18.13	0.00234	0.0183	0.000042822	62.4	0.0000007	0.0001	0.0068625
Average	34	---	0.034	0.00007956	65	0.0000012	---	0.01224

EDI*-Estimated Dietary Intake, H* =Concentration of the aldrin [mg/kg] , HQ* =Hazard Quotient , ADI* =Acceptable Daily Intake WHO JMPR 1991

Table: 3.2.b: Summary of Estimated daily intake and hazard quotient in various subpopulations based on fish consumption rate for dieldrin in Channa sp.

Fish Consumption rate	Average Consumption per day in grams	H=0.03024 (mg/kg)	Average Consumption per day in Kg ©	H×C	Average body weight B.W.	EDI=H*C/B.W	ADI	HQ=EDI/ADI
Once in 3 days	65	0.03024	0.065	0.0019656	69	0.0000285	0.0001	0.284869565
Once in a month	8.2	0.03024	0.008	0.00024192	63.3	0.0000038	0.0001	0.038218009
Once in a week	42.85	0.03024	0.0429	0.001297296	64.5	0.0000201	0.0001	0.201131163
Once in 15 days	18.13	0.03024	0.0183	0.000553392	62.4	0.0000089	0.0001	0.088684615
Average	34	-	0.034	0.00102816	65	0.0000158	-	0.158178462

EDI*-Estimated Dietary Intake, H* =Concentration of the dieldrin [mg/kg] , HQ* =Hazard Quotient,ADI* =Acceptable Daily Intake WHO JMPR 1991.

Lifetime cancer risk Assessment

Acceptable lifetime cancer risk range for environmental contaminants is 10^{-6} to 10^{-4} , Risks

below 10^{-6} are generally negligible. Risks above 10^{-4} often require mitigation or cleanup actions. ; (US EPA, 2015). In our study we found LCR for aldrin and dieldrin in Channa is 1×10^{-5} and 1.26×10^{-4} respectively.

Table 3.3- Summary of Life time cancer risk assessment for aldrin and dieldrin pesticides in muscle tissue of Channa sp.

<i>Pesticide Residue</i>	<i>Concentration of Pesticides in mg/kg</i>	<i>Average consumption per day¹ (kg/Day)</i>	<i>EDI (mg/kg·day)</i>	$LADD = EDI \times \frac{ED}{AT}$ <i>(mg/kg·day)²</i>	$CR = LADD \times CSF^3$
<i>Aldrin</i>	0.00234	0.034	1.2×10^{-6}	6.0×10^{-7}	1×10^{-5}
<i>Dieldrin</i>	0.03024	0.034	1.58×10^{-5}	7.9×10^{-6}	1.26×10^{-4}

1Based on data collected, 2 LADD,- USEPA 3 CSF as per 1987 US EPA for aldrin is 17mg/day, for dieldrin 16mg/day

Discussion

Aldrin and Dieldrin pesticide residues in fish tissue pose potential health risks to humans. (Ezemonye et al., 2015) . The estimated average daily intake (EADI) for these pesticides in Clarias gariepinus exceeded the recommended reference dose, indicating a significant health risk. Hazard Quotient (HQ) values for both Aldrin and Dieldrin were greater than 1, suggesting potential toxicity from consumption. (Ezemonye et al., 2015). Aldrin was not detected in any of the rainbow trout samples from Lake Mashu, while dieldrin was present as a predominant residue among the dieldrin, endrin, and aldrin group. The estimated daily intake (EDI) of dieldrin for humans was calculated to be $0.08 \text{ ng kg}^{-1} \text{ day}^{-1}$, which is significantly lower than the acceptable daily intake (ADI) (Takazawa et al., 2007). In our study both aldrin and Dieldrin were detected in muscle tissue of Channa sp. Hazard quotient values for both the reference pesticides were in low risk level. Their detection more than 20 years after their ban in Indian

(since 2001) is a matter concern. The reason being bioaccumulation and

biomagnification. Dieldrin is highly persistent in nature. (Dieldrin, n.d.). It is not easily soluble in water but settles in sediments. (Xie et al., 2025). Fish Channa is a bottom feeder. The food item eaten by the Channa fish are insects, fishes, crustacean, molluscs, worms, animal matter, decayed organic matter, algae, plant matter, their gut content also showed sand, mud and miscellaneous items. (Chakraborty, et al., 2021). These feeding habits correlate with the level of Dieldrin fish tissue. Aldrin level in tissue was comparatively low, as it is converted to dieldrin in living systems.

As per the criteria described in EPA's final guidelines for assessment of carcinogenic risk (USEPA, 1986), dieldrin also may be classified in Group B2, probable human carcinogen. Again, under the more recent Proposed Guidelines for Carcinogen Risk Assessment (USEPA, 1996/1999), dieldrin would probably be categorized as "likely" to produce cancer in humans by the oral route of exposure, while its carcinogenic potential via other routes of exposure would merit a classification of "cannot be

determined due to inadequate data.” (EPA 2003) (US EPA, 2013). LCR of aldrin in our study is in Negligible range of risk value and dieldrin is in Acceptable lifetime cancer risk range for environmental contaminants. (when calculated as per the US EPA 1987 Guidelines). Thus, indicating a low life time cancer risk when consumed in moderate amount. Smaller sample size, data on limited consumption rate can be considered as the limitations of this study.

III. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Detection of aldrin and dieldrin in the fish *Channa* sp. is significant in assessing the persistent nature of dieldrin even after twenty years of its ban in India. Their unauthorised use as insecticide, sediment depositions along with bioaccumulation properties can be considered for the current level of pesticide in the tissue. Encouraging alternative strategies, pest control methods might help in controlling the use of pesticides in agriculture. Further analysis of sediment, blood sample analysis of sample group might help in assessing the exact status of pesticide level in the environment.

Conflict of Interest

The Authors have no conflict of interest to declare. Both the authors have seen the contents of the paper and no financial benefit is involved. This submission is original work of authors.

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